

SocialTruth - content verification for the digital society

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Outline

- Introduction
- SocialTruth project
- A few research results
- Conclusion

Introduction

- With the advent of digital media fake news became a real danger.
- Fake news is used to increase the interest of Internet users to encourage the increase of traffic to a given website.

Introduction

- Fake news has been recognized as an essential tool of political struggle.
- In addition to fake articles, falsified images or videos are increasingly used, often modified using DeepFake models.
- Today, disinformation is used widely as a weapon (e.g., during the current conflict triggered by Russia's brutal assault on Ukraine – see DeepFake with Volodymyr Zelensky calling on Ukrainians to surrender).

How to combat them

- Manual fact-checking
 - Expensive
 - May be biased
- Automatic fact-checking

SHARE OF AMERICANS VERY CONFIDENT IN THEIR ABILITY TO RECOGNIZE FAKE NEWS

26%

AMERICANS WHO BELIEVE FAKE NEWS CAUSES A GREAT DEAL OF CONFUSION

67%

AMERICANS WHO ACCIDENTALLY SHARED FAKE NEWS

38.2%

Motivations and expected benefits

SocialTruth - goals

- The SocialTruth aims to combat fake news using the latest technology.
- The project's originality is based on creating an open, democratic, pluralistic, and distributed ecosystem for easy access to various verification services, ensuring scalability, and building trust.

DATA RESULTS

Title: Sham Arizona 2020 review blows open Trump's election lies
Text: CNN | 9/24/2021 | Listen Sham Arizona 2020 review blows open Trump's election lies -- but he's trying again in Texas Analysis by Stephen Collinson, CNN Updated: Fri, 24 Sep 2021 05:09:25 GMT
Source: CNN Donald Trump's effort to destroy confidence in America's elections suffered a serious setback late Thursday after a draft of the sham review ordered by Arizona Republicans confirmed that he had lost to President Joe Biden in the state's critical Maricopa County. But the ex-President's relentle...
Date of analysis: 2021-09-24T11:59:07.876Z
Assessment: ★★☆☆

👍 Deep-CNN
👍 DeepNet + RF
👎 BERT + RNN
👎 LSTM RNN

SocialTruth

SocialTruth advantages

- **Open ecosystem** with standard interfaces and no vendor lock-in, favouring pluralism and the deployment of reusable, interoperable and interchangeable verification services.
- **Powered by blockchain technology**, for distributed reputation and trust, enhanced security and auditability, with no intermediaries and central authorities.
- **Expert meta-verification engines** with open design that can intelligently fuse multiple verification results.
- **Digital Companion** ensuring convenient access to both professional and individual users.
- **Lifelong Learning Machines** that constantly accumulate experience and learn new paradigms of fake news.

Architecture based on microservices

- Easiest implementation of new services, changes and updates – particularly important for frequent releases of the system that is developed in collaborative project.
- Better fitting to cloud-based approach and SocialTruth requirement of services decentralization.
- More suitable to use containers (e.g. Docker).
- Better suited for smaller (than large enterprise solutions) and well-partitioned, web-based systems,.
- Better addressing requirement of the SocialTruth extensibility.

Deployment options

- Decentralization.
- Each verification service deployed at a different hosting facility (e.g. different servers or clouds).
- Each uses the same standard interfaces to allow them to be easily accessible, reusable and interchangeable.
- Deployment options:
 - Public cloud
 - Private cloud
 - Community cloud
 - Hybrid cloud

Fake news detection from data streams

- To the best of the authors' knowledge, there is no work treating fake news detection as a problem of streaming data classification.
- Contribution:
 - Formulating the problem of fake news detection as a data stream classification task.
 - Proposing a novel pattern classification methods based on feature extraction techniques, which address the detection of fake news in streaming data from social media.

P. Ksieniewicz, P. Zyblewski, M. Choraś, R. Kozik, A. Giełczyk and M. Woźniak, "Fake News Detection from Data Streams," *2020 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, 2020, pp. 1-8, doi: 10.1109/IJCNN48605.2020.9207498.

Fake news detection from data streams

FEATURES	PCA			COUNT VECTORIZER			FEATURE SELECTION		
	GNB	MLP	HT	GNB	MLP	HT	GNB	MLP	HT
	SEA								
2	0.602	<u>0.666</u>	0.570	0.553	<u>0.628</u>	0.560	0.663	0.679	0.673
10	0.724	<u>0.743</u>	0.729	0.674	<u>0.715</u>	0.679	0.728	0.755	0.727
50	0.693	<u>0.770</u>	0.701	0.714	<u>0.728</u>	0.717	0.744	0.778	0.744
100	0.659	<u>0.759</u>	0.659	0.704	<u>0.718</u>	0.705	0.753	0.762	0.749
200	0.656	<u>0.692</u>	0.671	0.716	<u>0.733</u>	0.693	0.758	0.764	0.713
500	0.664	0.747	0.561	0.732	<u>0.733</u>	0.561	0.745	<u>0.746</u>	0.561
1000	0.635	<u>0.748</u>	0.561	0.667	0.761	0.561	0.667	<u>0.750</u>	0.561
	ONLINE BAGGING								
2	0.516	0.641	<u>0.664</u>	0.517	0.604	<u>0.612</u>	0.636	0.677	0.688
10	0.597	0.704	<u>0.719</u>	0.621	0.667	<u>0.713</u>	0.708	0.732	0.730
50	0.613	0.768	0.711	0.657	0.695	<u>0.745</u>	0.706	0.728	<u>0.767</u>
100	0.578	<u>0.768</u>	0.694	0.641	0.705	<u>0.738</u>	0.697	0.740	0.771
200	0.569	<u>0.754</u>	0.658	0.650	<u>0.758</u>	0.708	0.691	0.764	0.738
500	0.559	0.804	0.589	0.673	<u>0.785</u>	0.633	0.722	<u>0.792</u>	0.616
1000	0.555	0.819	0.561	0.715	<u>0.818</u>	0.625	0.716	<u>0.810</u>	0.619
	SINGLE MODEL								
2	0.512	0.633	<u>0.654</u>	0.518	0.595	<u>0.611</u>	0.634	0.673	0.690
10	0.595	0.700	<u>0.702</u>	0.622	0.662	<u>0.707</u>	0.710	0.727	0.694
50	0.618	0.768	<u>0.672</u>	0.644	0.697	<u>0.730</u>	0.707	0.727	0.747
100	0.579	0.766	0.663	0.645	0.705	<u>0.722</u>	0.696	0.742	<u>0.745</u>
200	0.562	<u>0.752</u>	0.667	0.651	<u>0.753</u>	0.714	0.686	0.762	0.724
500	0.556	0.796	0.618	0.672	<u>0.777</u>	0.661	0.719	<u>0.788</u>	0.630
1000	0.554	0.808	0.615	0.722	<u>0.806</u>	0.626	0.722	<u>0.805</u>	0.626

Alphabet Flattening

Alphabet Flattening as a variant of n-gram feature extraction method in ensemble classification of fake news.

APPROACH	INPUT SENTENCE	n -GRAM DICTIONARIES	
		UNIGRAM	BIGRAM
WORDS	<i>The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog</i>	{"The":1, "quick":1, "brown":1, "fox":1, "jumps":1, "over":1, "the":1, "lazy":1, "dog":1} <i>9 tokens</i>	{"The quick":1, "quick brown":1, "brown fox":1, "fox jumps":1, "jumps over":1, "over the":1, "the lazy":1, "lazy dog":1} <i>8 tokens</i>
AF	<i>aaa aaaaa aaaaa aaa aaaaa aaaa aaa aaaa aaa</i>	{"aaa":4, "aaaa":3, "aaaa":2 } <i>3 tokens</i>	{"aaa aaaaa":2, "aaaa aaaaa":1, "aaaa aaa":1, "aaaa aaa":2, "aaa aaaa":1} <i>6 tokens</i>

Alphabet Flattening

Experimental evaluation -- backed up by the statistical analysis -- conducted to assess the quality of the classifier ensembles employing Alphabet Flattening in the processing shows that it can be a useful improvement of the multiple classifier systems for NLP.

Multilingual Data Classification

This work deals with NLP and introduces a training procedure for a fake news detection model that can classify news provided in different languages and perform knowledge transfer between them.

J.Kozal, M.Leś, P.Ksieniewicz, P.Zyblewski, M.Woźniak, Lifelong Learning Natural Language Processing Approach for Multilingual Data Classification, ECML/PKDD 2022 (under review)

Multilingual Data Classification

Multilingual Data Classification

Table 2. Accuracy for each extractor trained and evaluated on one dataset for text attribute.

DATASET	EXTRACTION METHOD				
	TF-IDF 1	LDA 2	<i>mult</i> 3	BERT <i>eng</i> 4	<i>spa</i> 5
<i>kaggle</i>	.866	.911	.981	.985	—
	—	1	1, 2	1, 2, 3	—
<i>esp fake</i>	.751	.618	.786	—	.853
	2	—	2	—	1, 2, 3
<i>mixed</i>	.729	.768	.972	.974	.982
	—	1	1, 2	1, 2	1, 2, 3, 4

Conclusion

- SocialTruth aims to benefit individual users by testing content credibility on social media and stopping disinformation.
- The project aims to help media organizations, content authors, and journalists improve their research resources with a better option to match different media sources and create a more sustainable, quality, and safety-oriented network and social media ecosystem.
- The advantage of the architecture lies in its openness so that other services (methods, e.g., for image analysis) can be added and run on the deployed platform.

Conclusion

- www.socialtruth.eu
- twitter.com/SocialTruth
- https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=J1cY21i6B_o